

Influence of Temperature and Light Intensity on Photosynthesis and Respiration and an Explanation of "Solarisation" and "Compensation Point"

BY N. R. DHAR.

It is well known that the Arrhenius equation $\log e K_1/K_2 = A(T_1 - T_2)/T_1 T_2$ is applicable to ordinary chemical reactions taking place in a homogeneous system (K_1 and K_2 are the velocities of the reaction at T_1 and T_2 absolute temperatures and A is a constant).

In a previous publication (Dhar, *Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1920, 23, 44) it was shown that the application of the above Arrhenius relation connecting velocity and temperature of a reaction is certainly more correct than to apply the van't Hoff rule that the temperature coefficient of a chemical reaction for a 10° rise of temperature lies between 2 and 3, because the temperature coefficient does not remain constant at different temperature intervals but falls off with increase of temperature. Moreover, Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 707) has shown that for some reactions, the temperature coefficient can have the value 7.2 for a 10° rise.

Many plant physiologists following the lead of Blackman have applied the van't Hoff rule to plant temperature studies. Thus Stiles states, "Many plant and animal processes have been shown to obey the van't Hoff rule, if only approximately and within limits," and "similar curves for the respiration of higher plants have been constructed by Kuijper, who found the van't Hoff rule followed between 0° and 20°" ("Photosynthesis", 1925, p. 100). The application of the Arrhenius relation has been found to be general with ordinary chemical reactions. When the same relation is applied to the results actually obtained regarding the influence of temperature on photosynthesis in plants, it fails, as will be evident from the following table obtained from Warburg's results (*Biochem. Z.*, 1919, 100, 259).

Light intensity.	Observed $\frac{K_1 + 10}{K_1}$	Calc. $\frac{K_1 + 10}{K_1}$
16	2.0	4.11 between 16° and 25° (taking 4.7 between 5° and 10°)
45	2.1	4.01 between 10° and 20° (taking 4.3 between 5.4 and 10°)
45	1.6	3.66 between 20° and 30° (taking 4.3 between 5.4 and 10°)

The results have been calculated by applying the Arrhenius relation. It appears that the temperature coefficients of photosynthesis do not obey the Arrhenius relation, which has been found to be universally applicable to ordinary chemical reactions investigated so far and no case of failure has been reported. In photosynthesis the observed values are always smaller than the calculated values. The reasons of the non-applicability of this relation to photosynthesis in plants are, (i) the greater influence of temperature on the respiration process than that on photosynthesis, and, (ii) the harmful influence of high temperatures on the chloroplasts.

It has already been stated that when the temperature of a plant system undergoing photosynthesis is increased the velocity of photosynthesis increases but to a smaller extent than that of respiration. Consequently, the temperature coefficient of the observed photosynthesis will appear to be smaller than when the reversible reaction was not present. Moreover, the chloroplast in the protoplasmic cells which is likely to be active in the photosynthetic process starts undergoing deterioration when the temperature is greater than 20° and may be partially destroyed when the temperature is still greater. This is evident on comparing the results obtained by Warburg (*loc. cit.*) and those calculated from the Arrhenius relation. The observed temperature coefficients between 16° and 25° and between 10° and 20° are nearly half of the calculated values, whilst the observed temperature coefficient between 20° and 30° is much less than half of the calculated value. The pernicious influence of high temperature on physiological, enzyme, and bacterial processes is well known. In most cases the optimum temperature in these reactions is round about 20° . Moreover, in plant photosynthesis, there is an additional factor, namely, the reverse reaction, *e.g.*, respiration, which is also simultaneously going on and is counterbalancing the photosynthetic reaction and hence the influence of temperature on photosynthesis is less pronounced due to these counteracting agencies.

It has already been stated that in the case of some chemical reactions, the temperature coefficient can have the high value 7.2. Hence it is no wonder that the temperature coefficient of photosynthesis at low temperatures (between 5° and 10°) has the value 4.3. It seems probable that the photosynthetic reaction is not an adsorption process of which the average temperature coefficient is in the neighbourhood of 1.2 for a 10° rise of temperature, but it is controlled by a truly,

photochemical change having a moderately high temperature coefficient. In several communications from these laboratories it has been shown that photochemical reactions need not have temperature coefficients approaching unity but can have values as high as 4 (*cf.* Dhar, "Chemical action of light", 1931, pp. 314-318). From the foregoing considerations, it is clear that it is needless to assume that the photosynthetic process involves two reactions. It is believed that in the high light intensity, the chemical reaction ("Blackman reaction" as designated by Warburg) is determining the total velocity of the reaction, because for a rise of temperature between 15° and 25°, the velocity of the photosynthesis is doubled. On the other hand, in low light intensity the temperature coefficient instead of being 2 as with intense light, is 1.06 and hence it has been assumed that the chemical reaction is not the controlling factor as in the previous case; but the photochemical reaction with a low temperature coefficient determines the photosynthetic rate at low intensities of light.

In presence of intense light, the photochemical reaction causing photosynthesis and having a moderately large temperature coefficient, is predominant and the counteracting influence of the respiration process, which is not as much accelerated by light as the photosynthetic reaction, is not prominent. On the other hand, in presence of feeble illumination, the velocity of the photosynthetic reaction is not high, because this reaction takes place only in light and is proportional to the light intensity. In this case, the counteracting influence of respiration, especially at increased temperatures, becomes prominent and hence the influence of temperature on the observed photosynthetic rate is feeble.

Warburg (*loc. cit.*, p. 258) has observed that the temperature coefficient of photosynthesis with the unicellular *alga chlorella* is much less when the light intensity is feeble than when it is strong. Thus $k_t + 10/k_t$ between 16° and 25° with a light intensity 16=2.0, and $k_t + 10/k_t$ between 15° and 25° with a relative intensity of 1=1.06.

These results which appeared to have been confirmed by other workers can be explained in the following way:

It has already been stated that in a plant, the following opposing reactions are taking place

and the temperature coefficient of photosynthesis is less than that of respiration. Hence, when the light intensity is feeble, the velocity of photosynthesis is small and is slightly greater than that of respiration at the same temperature. Now when the temperature of the system is raised through 10° (say), the velocity of the photosynthesis will be increased to a smaller extent than that of respiration. Consequently the temperature coefficient of the observed photosynthesis may be unity or less.

It will be interesting to note in this connection that Harder (*Jahrb. Wiss. Bot.*, 1915, 56, 281) working with low light intensity and sea plants of the polar region obtained the following ratio between photosynthesis and respiration for different temperatures.

20° - 22°	0.5882	0.4227	0.4280
2° - 3.5°	1.603	0.9207	2.059

Moreover, in nature when the temperature of the air is high, the plants gain no material through photosynthesis because of the high respiration, whilst at lower temperatures with the same light intensity, food materials are formed in the plant.

Willstätter and Stoll ("Kohlensäure Assimilation", 1918) have reported that leaves of low chlorophyll content exhibit a lower acceleration with increasing temperature than the leaves of high chlorophyll content. Thus leaves of *ulmus* with low chlorophyll content showed a temperature coefficient of 1.34 and with a high chlorophyll content of 1.53 between 15° and 25° . These results of Willstätter and Stoll can be explained from the view point already advanced.

The important researches of Willstätter and Stoll show that although there are minor discrepancies, the rate of photosynthesis is determined by the chlorophyll content of the plant. Hence, in presence of large amounts of chlorophyll in the leaves, the velocity of the photochemical reaction involved in the photosynthetic process will be larger than in the case of leaves containing smaller quantities of chlorophyll. In the case of leaves containing large amounts of chlorophyll, the direct photochemical process being high, the reverse reaction of respiration will appear to be less pronounced and this case is comparable to the case previously discussed with high light intensity, and hence a temperature increase will lead to an increase of photosynthesis. On the other hand, in presence of small amounts of chlorophyll in the leaves, the photosynthetic rate is low and hence the opposing respiration reaction will appear to be prominent and this

case is allied to photosynthesis with low light intensity having a small temperature coefficient.

Willstätter and Stoll obtained the following interesting results.

Photosynthesis of the green and yellow varieties of Elm.
5% CO₂ and 24000 Lux.

Variety.	Temp.	Dry wt. of leaves.	Leaf sur- face.	Chlorophyll.	Photosynthesis	
					g. CO ₂ /hour.	
					8 g. fresh leaves.	1 sq. m. surface
Chlorophyll poor	25°	2.00 g.	321 sq. cm.	0.95mg.	0.075	2.3
„ „	15°	2.00	321	0.95	0.056	1.7
Chlorophyll rich	25°	2.35	421	13.0	0.089	2.1
„ „	15°	2.35	421	13.0	0.058	1.4

The foregoing results show that the temperature coefficient (1.53) of the photosynthesis with chlorophyll-rich leaves is greater than that with chlorophyll-poor leaves (1.34), although the photosynthesis is not at all proportional to the amount of chlorophyll in the leaves. Willstätter and Stoll find that temperature variations do not affect the rate of photosynthesis of the yellow varieties, as much as the normal ones. In the yellow varieties, the amount of photosynthesis being small, the compensating influence of respiration becomes prominent and hence temperature does not appear to influence photosynthesis with these varieties to the same extent as the normal ones with more chlorophyll.

Moreover, differences in light intensity have more profound effect on the yellow varieties than on the normal ones and the time factor appears more slowly than in the normal ones. It is well known that photosynthesis increases with the light intensity and the chlorophyll content of the leaves. Now in the case of leaves containing much chlorophyll, the velocity of photosynthesis will be high and may reach the maximum, even when the light intensity is not high and hence in these cases, the reaction will be less sensitive to the influence of light changes, because the reaction is already fast due to the presence of large amounts of chlorophyll. On the other hand, when the chlorophyll content is small, the reaction velocity is small and light will affect the velocity more markedly than in the previous case. This

explanation is in agreement with the observations of Willstätter and Stoll that in the chlorophyll-rich leaves, an increase of light intensity was without influence on photosynthesis ; in fact the light intensity could be reduced by $\frac{3}{8}$ without affecting the rate of photosynthesis. Exactly similar exhaustion effect has been observed with several photochemical reactions where the velocity of the reaction may be proportional to $l^{\frac{1}{2}}$ or $l^{\frac{1}{4}}$ in some cases where the reaction is very fast (cf. Bhattacharya and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 197, 523).

Respiration—the most Fundamental of Plant Processes.

It seems that in plants, as much as in animals, respiration is the most fundamental process, that is going on in the plant system. Photosynthetic activity is a subsidiary reaction, in comparison with respiration. It appears that the various processes, which are associated with plant life can only take place as long as respiration lasts.

The activity of a plant is measured by its respiration. It appears that the greater the rate of respiration per unit surface, the greater is the activity of the plant. The amount of respiration would depend on (i) the concentration of carbohydrates and other food materials available in the plant, (ii) a minimum oxygen pressure, and, (iii) the activity of the enzymes and inductors. When factors (ii) and (iii) are constant, respiration will depend on the concentration of carbohydrates, proteins and other food materials, which is controlled by the photosynthetic activity of the plant.

The view that respiration is more fundamental in plant life than photosynthesis is supported from the following observations.

Warburg (*Biochem. Z.*, 1919, 100, 264) has reported that, while respiration is not influenced by different partial pressures of oxygen above a certain minimum, photosynthesis is less at higher pressures. A change in the partial pressure of oxygen from $\frac{1}{50}$ to 1 atmosphere reduces the photosynthetic rate by about $\frac{1}{3}$.

Wurmser and Jacquot (*Bull. Soc. Chim. biol.*, 1923, 5, 305; 1924, 6, 169) have observed that when certain marine algae are subjected to temperatures from 36° to 45° for 1 to 15 minutes, the rate of photosynthesis is always depressed when the plants are returned to the temperature of the environment (16°). Similar effects are produced with glycerol. Warburg has shown that photosynthetic rate

is reduced by hydrocyanic acid and urethanes in extreme dilutions in which the respiratory activity is not affected and in certain cases, even stimulated. It appears, therefore, that photosynthetic process is more sensitive than that of respiration. As all plant processes depend on respiration, which is the vital reaction in plant life as much as in animal life, photosynthetic activity cannot proceed without respiration taking place in the plant and hence, without the presence of oxygen, which supports respiration in both plant and animal life. Because lack of oxygen is detrimental to respiration, it is also harmful to photosynthesis. Consequently the classical experiments of Boussingoult (*Agronomie chimie agricole et physiologie*, 1868, 4, 329) and Pringsheim (*Sitz. preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, 1887, 763) showing that in an atmosphere of hydrogen, nitrogen, carbon dioxide, or methane, plants lose the power of photosynthesis, are easily explained from the above viewpoint, because in presence of these gases, oxygen respiration stops. It appears, therefore, that besides light, chlorophyll, carbon dioxide and moisture supply, respiration is also necessary for photosynthesis.

Willstätter and Stoll have observed that various plants exhibit a wide variation in their resistance to lack of oxygen. According to Willstätter and Stoll, the partial pressure of oxygen can be reduced to 1/100th of that in air without affecting photosynthesis if the rest of the atmosphere is nitrogen. After complete displacement of oxygen for 2 hours, the leaves on illumination cannot effect photosynthesis, although under these conditions, the leaves show no visible signs of injury. When *cyclamen europaeum*, *polytrichum juniperinum* are exposed to oxygen-free atmosphere for 1 hour, the photosynthetic activity is decreased but not entirely stopped. When the plants are kept in oxygen-free atmosphere for 15 to 24 hours, they show no photosynthesis immediately on illumination, but after $\frac{1}{2}$ hour or so, photosynthesis begins and continues to a high rate. Long continued exposure to oxygen-free atmosphere produces injurious effects on the photosynthetic mechanism. The longer the time of exposure of a plant to an atmosphere free from oxygen, the lower is the rate of subsequent photosynthesis and more incomplete the recovery. Willstätter and Stoll have concluded from their careful experiments that oxygen is essential for photosynthesis but a small quantity of oxygen is enough. Now, as soon as photosynthesis begins, oxygen is generated and respiration goes on. Lack of oxygen produces a permanent injury

to the plant, because respiration stops in the absence of oxygen.

Moreover, it appears from the foregoing results, that for plants, the oxygen requirements for respiration is less than in animals and they resist lack of oxygen in their living atmosphere much better than animals.

It has already been stated that the activity of a plant is measured by the amount of its respiration per unit surface. Consequently, the greater the respiration, the greater the activity of the plant and greater the photosynthesis, because photosynthesis, like other plant processes, is associated with the activity of the plant. It has already been stated that in plants, Willstätter and Stoll did not find any proportionality between the chlorophyll content and its photosynthetic activity. This is explained from the viewpoint advanced here that the respiratory activity of the plant is the most vital of the plant processes and all other functions of the plant depend on the respiratory activity and consequently, photosynthetic rate is likely to be more directly proportional to the respiratory activity than to any other single factor, e. g., chlorophyll content, light intensity or carbon dioxide concentration. Experiments are in agreement with this viewpoint. Plaster (*Beit. Biol. Pflanzen*, 1912, 11, 249) showed that the leaves of the light green or yellow varieties have a lower rate of photosynthesis and respiration than the varieties rich in chlorophyll. Although, there is no parallelism between chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate, the ratio between respiration and photosynthesis appears to be constant as will be evident from the following results obtained by Plaster with the light green varieties: *ptelea* = 1.77, *catalpa* = 1.72, *mirabilis* = 2.0, *ulmus* = 2, *populus* = 2.1. Similar results correlating respiration and photosynthetic rate have been obtained by Miss Henrici (*Inaug. Disert. Basel*, 1918, 90, "Chlorophyll Gehalt und Kohlensäure Assimilation bei Alpen-Eben pflanzen") with alpine and low land plants, Boysen-Jensen (*Bot. tids.*, 1918, 36, 219) and Spoehr and McGee (*Carnegie Inst. of Wash. Pub.* 1923, No. 325, 76).

Willstätter and Stoll have also studied the photosynthetic activity of leaves of different ages. They have compared the activity of a light green leaf from the end of a branch with that of a dark green leaf from the base of the same branch. Their results are given below.

Photosynthesis of leaves from the same plant but in different stages of development at 25°, 5% CO₂ and 4800 Lux.

Species.	Date:	Description of leaves.	10 G. fresh leaves.		Photosynthesis g. CO ₂ /hour.		Photo-synthetic number P _c
			dry wt.	chlorophyll.	per 1. g. dry wt.	per 1 sq. dm. leaf area.	
<i>Acer pseudo-platanus</i>	June 23	4th-6th leaf from end of branch	3.3 g.	8.3mg.	0.030	0.016	11.8
...	June 24	From base of branch	3.58	40.0	0.058	0.026	5.2
<i>Tilia cordata</i>	June 25	Young light green	2.66	6.5	0.036	0.018	14.2
--	June 26	Lower dark green from same branch	3.19	28.1	0.058	0.028	6.6
<i>Laurus</i>	June 30	Light green leaves	3.10	12.7	0.024	0.019	5.9
<i>Nobilis</i>	July 1	Dark green leaves of previous year	4.95	21.2	0.023	0.023	3.7

The foregoing results of Willstätter and Stoll on the photosynthetic activity of leaves in different stages of development show that although the chlorophyll content of the leaves increases and the photosynthetic activity also increases, the two are not parallel. Consequently, it is clear that with the young leaves, the photosynthetic activity is exceedingly high and is not proportional to their chlorophyll content, because the respiratory activity of the young leaves is also very high. In other words, the greater the respiratory activity (metabolism), the greater is the photosynthetic activity.

The photosynthetic activity of etiolated plants in which the chlorophyll is just developing, shows the disproportionality between photosynthesis and chlorophyll content. Willstätter and Stoll, using cultures of *phaseolus vulgaris* and *zea mays*, found that they are remarkably active, as soon as the first traces of chlorophyll are formed in light. Thus *phaseolus* with a chlorophyll content of 0.7 mg. per 10 grams of fresh leaves, had a photosynthetic number (P_c) of 133, whilst the control plants grown in light with 18.6 mg. of chlorophyll per 10 g_s of leaves showed a photosynthetic number of 9.4. In general, the photosynthetic number of etiolated

leaves is much higher than that of young leaves, which developed in the light. This is certainly due to the fact that the respiratory activity of the etiolated leaves is much greater than that of young leaves which developed in light.

Influence of Iron Compounds on Plant Respiration.

Moreover, the relation of photosynthesis and chlorophyll content of chlorotic plants is of great interest from this point of view. When plants grow in the absence of materials containing iron salts, they become very pale green or colourless with limited development of chloroplasts. This happens even under conditions of high illumination intensity. It has already been emphasised that respiration is the most fundamental and vital of the plant processes and factors, which inhibit respiration, also interfere with normal development and growth of plants. It is well known that iron compounds are of great importance to respiration in the animal kingdom. Dhar and collaborators (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 376, 799; 1930, 34, 711, 737) have shown that food materials are readily oxidised by air or hydrogen peroxide in presence of iron compounds. The iron present in animal blood accelerates the metabolism of food materials in the body. Consequently when the iron content of the blood decreases or the amount of red blood corpuscles becomes less, metabolism of food materials becomes defective; the person suffers from anaemia or chlorosis. Under these circumstances, iron compounds are used as medicine and these help metabolism.

In plant life also, in the absence of iron compounds, respiration becomes defective and hence the vital activities and growth of the plant are hindered and it becomes chlorotic and poor in chlorophyll content. As the respiratory activity is defective in chlorotic plants, it is expected that its photosynthetic power will also be anomalous. This is borne out from the experiments of Willstätter and Stoll, who cultivated plants with nutrient solutions containing no iron. While other types of leaves, also poor in chlorophyll, such as the light green or yellow varieties, autumnal and etiolated leaves, showed high photosynthetic activity in comparison with their chlorophyll content, the chlorotic leaves have a low rate of photosynthesis. Hence photosynthesis goes hand in hand with respiratory activity. It is interesting to note here the

observations of Curtel (*Compt. rend.*, 1900, 130, 1074) who has observed that chlorotic plants have a lower rate of respiration and transpiration than normal plants.

The important fact brought out by the investigation of Willstätter and Stoll is that the leaves of light green or yellow variety, as far as photosynthesis is concerned, are affected more by differences in light intensity, while the leaves rich in chlorophyll are more sensitive to changes of temperature. These results have already been explained in the foregoing pages from our viewpoint of the opposing influence of respiration on photosynthesis.

In explaining these and other results Willstätter and Stoll have been led to the assumption of the existence of an internal factor or protoplasmic factor, which is supposed to be of an enzymatic nature. The author has put forth the view that this internal factor is really the respiratory activity or metabolic activity of the plant, which is also probably of an enzymatic nature and may depend on the presence of inductors.

Influence of Age on Plant Processes.

It is a well established fact that metabolism (carbon dioxide output) per unit area decreases with age in the animal world (cf. Dhar, "New Conceptions in Bio-Chemistry", 1932). In plant kingdom the same relation is observed. From the quantitative work of Willstätter and Stoll on the relations between the rate of photosynthesis, chlorophyll formation and respiration, it is clear that respiratory activity is very high in very young leaves and it decreases with time and development of the leaf. Young leaves have an exceedingly high rate of respiration, which decreases to one-fourth of this rate when the leaf matures. In general, functional activity decreases with age. Under favourable conditions of temperature and light, the development of chlorophyll is rapid. Willstätter and Stoll have observed an increase in photosynthesis with increase in chlorophyll content. There is, however, no direct proportionality between chlorophyll content and photosynthetic rate, as shown in the following table. (Results of Willstätter and Stoll.)

Rate of photosynthesis, chlorophyll content and photosynthetic number at 25°.

5 % CO₂, about 48,000 Lux.

Date.	Species.	From 10 g. fresh leaves.		Photosynthesis g. CO ₂ / hour.		Photosynthetic number P _c .
		dry wt.	chlorophyll.	per g. dry wt.	per 1 sq. dm.	
April 29.	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	2.10 g.	10.1 mg.	0.054	0.043	11.1
May 7		2.06	15.1	0.088	0.039	12.1
June 3		2.94	24.7	0.054	0.033	6.4
Oct 8		3.62	31.2	0.041	0.044	4.8
May 1	<i>Sambucus nigra</i>	1.85	11.7	0.078	0.046	12.2
May 8		2.25	23.1	0.101	0.057	9.8
July 14		2.56	23.5	0.057	0.032	6.2

With time, the dry weight of the leaves increases and on the basis of the dry weight, there is a decrease in photosynthesis. The leaves also show a consistent increase in chlorophyll content but this does not involve an increase in photosynthesis. Similar results have been obtained with other leaves.

It is well known that the longevity of cold blooded animals is much greater than that of warm blooded ones of the same size. Moreover, amongst warm blooded animals, the longevity of smaller animals is in general less than that of large animals. Also the duration of life varies inversely as the rate of energy expenditure during its continuance. In short, the length of life depends inversely as the rate of living. These results can be explained from the view point that the greater the activity of the cells and the body enzymes, the less is the duration of their active life. It has been frequently noted in catalytic operations that the duration of active catalytic influence of a highly active catalyst is short (*cf.* Dhar, "New Conceptions in Bio-Chemistry", 1932).

These conclusions appear to be applicable to the plant kingdom. In studying the influence of temperature on photosynthesis, it has been observed that the maximum velocity of photosynthesis cannot be maintained for a long time, but that with time, this maximum rate shifts to a lower temperature. This time factor is of great interest in plant physiology. In leaves poor in chlorophyll, *i.e.*, the

light green or yellow varieties, the time factor appears more slowly than in leaves rich in chlorophyll. It has already been stated that chlorophyll-rich leaves are more active towards photosynthesis and respiration than the yellow varieties of leaves. Hence the duration of the activity of the chlorophyll-rich leaves at a definite temperature is expected to be less than that of the comparatively inactive variety of leaves containing smaller amounts of chlorophyll. Consequently, the time factor appears more slowly in the less active yellow leaves than in the active chlorophyll-rich leaves. In other words, the activity of the chlorophyll-rich leaf will last for a shorter time than that of the chlorophyll-poor leaf.

The Phenomenon of "Solarisation".

It is well known that not only high temperature but also long exposure to strong light affects photosynthetic activity. Thus Ursprung (*Ber. Bot. Ges.*, 1917, 35, 57) observed that a leaf of *phaseobus* after 5 hours of illumination showed very deep colouration of the starch iodine, while after 8½ hours illumination, the reaction was faint. This phenomenon can be observed with almost any source of light of sufficient intensity and the time required is proportional to the light intensity. The effect is first brought about in the red orange portion, the region showing the best photosynthetic activity. With higher intensity, the shorter wave-lengths bring about in shorter time and it is apparently proportional to the photosynthetic activity of light. Ursprung (*loc. cit.*) has called this phenomenon "solarisation," as it is analogous to the phenomenon of polarisation observed in photographic plates under similar circumstances.

It is expected that not only with starch but with other carbohydrates, similar effect will be observed. This behaviour has been ascribed to the inactivation of chloroplasts. After long exposure to intense light, the plant organs are assumed not to function, although they are not killed and on keeping in the dark for a period, again produce starch normally.

The inhibiting effect of long exposure to light of high intensity on photosynthesis has also been studied by Ewart (*Ann. Bot.*, 1897, 11, 439; 1898, 12, 379) and the inhibiting effect has been ascribed to the destruction of chlorophyll. Pantanelli (*Jahrb. Wiss. Bot.*, 1908, 29, 167) explains the fatigue effects observed by him in bright

light from the view points of chlorophyll destruction and injury to the chloroplast plasma. The observations of Ewart on *allium cepa*, which does not form starch, indicate that when leaves of this plant are exposed to bright light for 14 days or for a shorter period while being fed with sugar, the evolution of oxygen finally ceases. This inactivation apparently does not injure the cells or chloroplasts. After a few days in darkness, the capacity for photosynthesis is regained.

The foregoing facts are explained from the following considerations.

In plants the following equilibrium exists :

The direct action (photosynthesis) is being opposed by the reverse reaction (respiration), which will increase, according to the law of mass action, with increase in the concentration of the carbohydrate, which is a product of photosynthesis. Consequently with accumulation of carbohydrates or when the plants are fed with sugar, as was done by Ewart, photosynthesis is retarded and may stop altogether when the carbohydrate content becomes very high. When the illumination is high and it lasts for a long time, the carbohydrate content increases and along with it the respiration also increases, and thus the photosynthetic velocity falls off with time even when the illumination is continued. After a time, the respiration will more than counterbalance photosynthesis and the carbohydrates formed by the photosynthesis will be oxidised to carbon dioxide and water and will disappear on prolonged exposure. When the carbohydrates disappear, the photosynthesis will again begin. It has been known for a long time that the photosynthetic rate decreases with accumulation of the products of photosynthesis. Moreover, Saposchnikoff (*Ber. Bot. Ges.*, 1893, 11, 391) has demonstrated the inhibitory power of an accumulation of carbohydrates and that these cannot increase beyond a certain point. When the leaves of *vitis vinifera* contain 23 to 29% carbohydrates of the dry weight, photosynthesis ceases and respiration predominates. Saposchnikoff has shown that as carbohydrates accumulate, decrease of photosynthetic rate takes place, whilst a decrease in the carbohydrate content results in an increased photosynthesis. These results are evident from the view point of the reversible reactions already put forward,

Moreover, there are two other factors, which increase respiration, should be considered *viz.*, (i) influence of light intensity on the respiratory process, and (ii) influence of increased temperature caused by prolonged light absorption. In several publications, Dhar and collaborators (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 926; 1928, 32, 1263; 1930, 34, 993) have shown that food materials like starch, sugars, proteins, fats, etc., in aqueous solutions or suspensions are oxidised to carbon dioxide and water by simply passing air at the ordinary temperature in presence of sunlight. In absence of light, there is no oxidation. In presence of inductors like ferrous hydroxide cerous hydroxide, etc., the food materials are oxidised to carbon dioxide and water by air even in absence of light. In presence of sunlight, these oxidations are greatly increased. Hence, Dhar and collaborators have suggested that on light exposure the metabolism in the animal body is increased, because the food materials are oxidised to a great extent by air due to the absorption of light. It seems pretty certain that in plants also the respiration or the oxidation of carbohydrates and other food materials, which slowly proceeds in the dark due to the presence of enzymes and inductors, is accelerated on exposure to light. It is well known that several plants and flowers run a temperature higher than that of the surrounding air in the dark due to respiration (*cf.* Kostycher, "Plant Respiration", 1927, p. 12) and these may be roughly compared to warm blooded animals. In the dark, most plants resemble cold blooded animals and they undergo oxidation and the carbohydrates and other food materials are burnt away. In presence of strong light, the respiration velocity seems to be increased. Moreover, when the plant is exposed to strong light for a long time, the temperature of the plant is likely to increase and with increased temperature, the respiration velocity is markedly increased, because the influence of temperature seems to be more pronounced on respiration than on photosynthesis. Consequently, when a plant is exposed to bright light for a long time, respiration more than counterbalances photosynthesis due to the increased concentration of carbohydrates, increased velocity of respiration by the absorption of radiant energy in the form of light and increase in the temperature of the plant by the absorption of light and the conversion of the light rays to heat. Under these circumstances, plants may behave as animals, as far as metabolism is concerned.

Compensation Point.

The compensation point, *i.e.*, the light intensity at which the photosynthetic and respiratory activities of the plant compensate each other decreases with decrease of temperature as will be evident from the following table.

Name.	Intensity at 20°.	Intensity at 5°.
Spirogyra	174	28·7
Fontinalis	150	40
Cladophora	259·3	62·9
Cinclidotus	400	75

The foregoing results show that the light intensity which at 20° represented the compensation point produced an evolution of oxygen due to photosynthesis at 5°

With *Cladophora*, with increasing temperature, the compensation point rises more rapidly than the rate of respiration determined in the dark; an increase of temperature from 5° to 25° causes the respiration to become 4·8 times greater in the dark, whilst the light intensity increases to 6·69 times.

The foregoing results as well as other facts on the compensation point can be explained from the following considerations: (a) Photosynthesis is proportional to the light intensity, there being no photosynthesis in the dark. (b) Respiration takes place in the dark but is appreciably accelerated by light. (c) An increase of temperature affects respiration more markedly than photosynthesis.

The fact that the compensation point rises with increase of temperature is due to the greater increase of respiratory activity than photosynthetic activity with increased temperature. The respiratory activity of the plant, which counterbalances the photosynthetic process, increases much more than photosynthesis at higher temperatures and consequently the light intensity must be increased to cause more photosynthesis to counteract the increased respiratory activity. There is another reason for further increase in the respiratory activity of the plant. Hitherto, it has been assumed by most of the plant physiologists that the process of respiration is not accelerated by light. But it is evident from the researches of Dhar and collaborators that animal metabolism is markedly accelerated by light absorption. Hence, it seems pretty certain that the res-

piratory process taking place in plants is also accelerated by light. Consequently, the respiratory activity of the plant is accelerated by two agencies, *e.g.*, temperature and light intensity and thus the light intensity required for increased photosynthesis in order to counteract this high respiratory activity should be very high. Thus with increasing temperature, the compensation point should rise more rapidly than the rate of respiration because of its additional enhancement by light absorption and this is clearly borne out from the experiments on *cladophora* in which an increase of temperature from 5° to 25° causes the respiration to become 4·8 times greater when determined in the dark, whilst the light intensity increases 6·69 times for the compensation point.

It is evident that under certain circumstances, when the temperature is high and the light is intense, the compensation point may not be attained even with intense light and the plant will evolve carbon dioxide like an animal even in presence of light. This is likely to happen frequently in tropical countries where at the sea level, the heat rays of the sun become very prominent and the temperature of the plant will be high and photosynthesis cannot counterbalance respiration under these circumstances. At higher altitudes, the light rays are more active than at the sea level and it is expected that at these altitudes, very seldom, respiration will exceed photosynthesis in sunlight. These conclusions are corroborated from the experimental results of Harder (*Jahrb. Wiss. Bot.*, 1921, 60, 531) with sea plants in the polar zones where the light intensity is not very high (*vide* Harder's data recorded in p. 544). The position of the compensation point of a plant with reference to temperature is naturally of great importance to the life of the plants and its relation to the environment.

Harder has reported that conditions may exist in nature where at higher temperatures, the plant stores no material through photosynthesis on account of the high respiratory activity. While at lower temperatures with the same light intensity, food materials are formed in the plant by photosynthesis.

The experimental observation that compensation point varies with different plants is explained on the basis that the respiratory activity of the plant and its increment by temperature and light vary with different plants.

Starting with the same culture of *cladophora*, and keeping one portion in diffused light and another in direct sunlight, great differ-

ences in the compensation point are observed in a week. With *sinapis alba*, a plant growing in light, the compensation point is at 1.0 (Bunsen units $\times 100$) but a compensation point lying at only 0.2 is observed with *oxalis acetosella*, a shade plant. Previous illumination of the plant must be considered before any conclusion is drawn from determination of the compensation point, which varies considerably with previous illumination of the plant. It has been observed that under certain circumstances in *fontinalis*, photosynthesis more than counterbalances respiration when the illumination is only 10 Lux, whilst under other conditions, 150 Lux is insufficient to achieve this.

Under constant and high illumination, leaves of beach trees emit carbon dioxide at 6250 Lux; the sun trees, *robina*, requires 25 times more intense light for photosynthesis to exceed respiration than the shade tree *fagus*.

These experimental observations are explicable by considering the temperature of the trees growing in light is higher than that of trees growing in the shade. Hence, the respiratory activity of plants growing in shade is much less than that growing in light. Moreover, the respiration of plants growing in light is also accelerated by the light absorption. Consequently the light intensity required to cause the increased photosynthesis in order to counteract the enhanced respiration due to an increase of temperature and light absorption must be very high.

Moreover, there is another important consideration in the explanation of the higher compensation point of trees grown in light than in the shade. From our experience on the velocity of photochemical reactions taking place in strong light, it is generally observed that the velocity of the photochemical reaction is not directly proportional to the light intensity or the absorbed light but the velocity varies as I^n where n is less than unity. On the other hand, in presence of feeble light, the velocity varies as I^n , where n is unity or more. Consequently, from the quantitative experiments with ordinary photochemical reactions, it is clear that in presence of intense light, photochemical reactions utilise less amount of absorbed radiation than when the same reactions take place in less intense light. This is usually known as "exhaustion effect." It is clear, therefore, that in photosynthesis, the same relation is to be expected. This behaviour has been observed by Warburg (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 102, 246) in his experiments

on the efficiency of the photosynthetic process. It has been reported by Warburg that when plants are cultivated under conditions of high light intensity, they utilise only a small amount of the absorbed energy. Plants grown under conditions of low light intensity can utilise a relatively large proportion of the absorbed energy. Hence, the light intensity necessary to obtain the requisite velocity of photosynthesis required to counteract respiration in the case of plants growing in light will be greater than that required for plants cultivated in the shade. Hence by growing the same type of plant under conditions of high and low light intensity, one type apparently passes into the other within a short time and its photosynthetic efficiency and possibly respiratory activity are altered.

From the foregoing pages, it is clear that the contention of Plaetzer (*Verhandlungen Physik-Med. Ges.*, Würzburg N. F., 1917, 48, 31), that the value of the light intensity at the compensation point is not a function of the respiratory activity is not correct. Plaetzer in his consideration of the compensation point missed the important point that the respiratory activity is also accentuated by light and that it is more influenced by temperature than photosynthesis.

From these considerations, one thing comes out very prominently that respiration is of vital importance to plants and is more fundamental and important to plant life than photosynthesis, which predominates in the plant only under highly restricted conditions of temperature and light intensity. In other conditions beyond this limit, in light as well as in the dark, plant life enjoys respiratory activity as much as animal life. Hence it appears that respiratory activity controls plant life as animal life.

SUMMARY.

1. The Arrhenius relation connecting velocity and temperature of a reaction which is applicable to ordinary chemical reactions, is not valid in the case of the influence of temperature on photosynthesis in plants. The non-applicability of the Arrhenius relation to photosynthesis and many other phenomena in plant life can be explained from the following considerations:

(a) It appears that in plant life, the following opposing reactions are taking place,

The direct action (photosynthesis) is being opposed by the reverse reaction (respiration) which increases according to the law of mass action with increase in the concentration of carbohydrates formed from photosynthesis.

(b) There is reason to believe that the velocity of respiration in plants is appreciably accelerated by light.

(c) The influence of temperature on respiration appears to be greater than that on photosynthesis.

2. The greater influence of temperature on photosynthesis in presence of strong light than that in weak light can be explained from the foregoing considerations. Hence, it is needless to assume that there are two reactions involved in photosynthesis.

3. The observations of Willstätter and Stoll that *leaves of low chlorophyll content* show a lower acceleration of photosynthesis with increase in temperature than the leaves of high chlorophyll content, have also been explained from the same point of view.

4. The experiments of Willstätter and Stoll showing that in chlorophyll-rich leaves an increase of light intensity does not affect photosynthesis have been explained from the view point of "exhaustion effect" as observed in ordinary photochemical reactions.

5. That oxygen is essential for photosynthesis appears to be due to the fact that plant life depends on oxygen respiration and the activity of the plant and along with it its photosynthetic power depend on its respiratory activity.

6. The photosynthetic activity is exceedingly high in young leaves and is not proportional to the chlorophyll content. This is because that the respiratory activity of young leaves is very high. In plant life, as well as in animal life, metabolism decreases with age.

7. In plant life in the absence of iron compounds, respiration and photosynthesis become defective as in chlorotic plants, because iron compounds accelerate respiration.

8. It appears that the factor which really controls plant life is its respiratory or metabolic activity.

9. In the animal world, the length of life depends inversely as the rate of living. The duration of the catalytic activity of an active catalyst appears to be short. These considerations are applicable to plant life as well. In leaves poor in chlorophyll, the time factor appears more slowly than in chlorophyll-rich leaves. In other words, the activity of chlorophyll-rich leaves would last for a shorter period than that of chlorophyll-poor leaves.

10. The phenomenon of "solarisation", that is, the disappearance of carbohydrates formed from photosynthesis, after prolonged illumination appears to be due to respiration, that is, their oxidation by oxygen in presence of light. The respiration, that is, the oxidation of carbohydrates is also increased by increase of temperature caused by light absorption.

11. The compensation point, that is, the light intensity at which the photosynthetic and respiratory activity of plants compensate each other, decreases with decrease of temperature. A certain light intensity which at 20° represents the compensation point, causes an evolution of oxygen due to photosynthesis at 5°. In nature, under certain conditions and at high temperatures, the plant cannot store any material due to photosynthesis on account of high respiratory activity, whilst at low temperatures, the same light intensity, food materials are formed by photosynthesis. The above results have been explained from the following considerations. (i) Photosynthesis is proportional to the light intensity, there being no photosynthesis in dark. (ii) Respiration takes place in the dark but is appreciably accelerated by light. (iii) An increase in temperature affects respiration more markedly than photosynthesis.

12. Respiration appears to be the more fundamental reaction in plant and is more important to plant life than photosynthesis, which predominates in plants only under restricted conditions of temperature and light intensity.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

Received January 20, 1933.

